

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Two promising IRRI rice hybrids named in Vietnam

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Two promising IRRI rice hybrids have been named UTL 1 and UTL 2 by CLRRI and released for regional testing in some provinces in Vietnam. UTL 1 is hybrid IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-IR (IR64615 H) and UTL 2 is IR62829 A/IR29723-143-3-2-IR (IR64616 H).

UTL 1 has a growth duration of 117-120 d and is 115 cm tall; UTL 2 has a shorter duration (110 d) and is 90 cm tall. These hybrids significantly outyielded check varieties MTL 58, MTL 61, and IR64 during four seasons of tests at CLRRI (Table 1). In addition, they possess good grain quality compared with Chinese-developed hybrids Tap Giao 3 (TG3) and Quang Uu Thanh (QUT). Grain quality of UTL 1 is comparable to that of IR64, which is one of Vietnam's preferred varieties for export (Table 2).

UTL 1 and UTL 2 showed resistance to major insect pests and diseases under field conditions in Cuu Long Delta. Both, however, were susceptible to bacterial blight in the wet season if N fertilizer was applied at rates above 80 kg N/ha.

The newly named hybrids are being tested in northern Vietnam. UTL 1 has shown yield potential as high as that of the Chinese hybrids being grown in northern Vietnam, but its grain quality is preferred. CLRRI is producing UTL 1 and UTL 2 seed to meet the demands of provincial agriculture departments. ■

Table 1. Yield and standard heterosis of IRRI-bred hybrids released by CLRRI, Omon, Cantho, Vietnam.

Season ^a	Yield (t/ha)			LSD (0.05)	Standard heterosis (%)	
	UTL 1	UTL 2	Check		UTL 1	UTL 2
1990 WS	7.6	6.7	5.3 (MTL 58)	0.8	43.4	26.4
1990-91 DS	6.0	6.1	5.0 (MTL 61)	0.4	20.0	22.0
1991 WS	4.6	4.9	3.7 (IR64)	0.7	24.3	32.4
1992 WS	4.9	5.5	4.90 (IR64)	-	0.0	12.2

^aWS = wet season, DS = dry season.

Table 2. Grain quality characteristics of hybrids UTL 1 and UTL 2. Mekong Delta, Vietnam.

Characteristic	Hybrid				Check
	UTL 1	UTL 2	TG3	QUT	IR64
Kernel length (cm)	7.2	6.1	6.2	6.3	7.6
Kernel breadth (cm)	1.9	2.0	2.4	2.5	2.2
Length-breadth ratio	3.7	3.1	2.5	2.6	3.4
Milling percentage	80	78	77	77	77
White rice percentage	68	67	63	64	65
Head rice recovery (%)	38	37	35	53	48
White belly (grade)	5	5	9	9	5

Performance of VX83 in Vietnam

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Variety VX83 was selected from the cross IR8/IR22//IR19746-11-33 in a 10 × 10 complete diallel crossing set. VX83 has been recommended for the late spring, early summer, and summer-autumn rice crops in intensified farming systems in Vietnam. Using VX83 makes it possible to expand areas under winter crops such as maize, sweet potato, soybean, potato, and other vegetables.

VX83 yielded more grain than checks CR203 and CN₂ across two seasons, three yr, and six locations (see table). ■

Performance of VX83 and checks.^a Vietnam, 1989-91.

Site	Entry	Grain yield (t/ha)		
		1989	1990	1991
Duyenthai	VX83	5.8	5.8	5.7
	CR203	5.5	5.6	4.4
	CN ₂	4.0	3.9	3.7
Van Binh	VX83	5.2	4.9	5.2
	CR 203	5.1	4.9	4.0
	CN ₂	3.8	3.8	3.6
INSA	VX83	5.3	5.2	5.2
	CR203	5.2	5.1	4.0
	CN ₂	4.0	4.0	3.8
Cam Dien	VX83	5.2	5.0	5.2
	CR203	5.1	4.1	4.4
	MT32	4.1	3.6	-
Thieu Yen	VX83	-	5.0	5.0
	CR203	-	4.7	4.2
Phu Loc	VX83	-	4.9	5.0
	CR203	-	4.8	4.2

^aChecks = CR203, CN₂, and MT32.